

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 146

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 146

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 146:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! ^aPraise the LORD, O my soul! ² I will praise the LORD ^awhile I live; I will ^bsing praises to my God while I have my being. ³ ^aDo not trust in princes, In ¹mortal ^bman, in whom there is ^cno salvation. ⁴ His ^aspirit departs, he ^breturns to ¹the earth; In that very day his ^cthoughts perish. ⁵ How ^ablessed is he whose help is the God of Jacob, Whose ^bhope is in the LORD his God, ⁶ Who ^amade heaven and earth, The ^bsea and all that is in them; Who ^ckeeps ¹faith forever; ⁷ Who ^aexecutes justice for the oppressed; Who ^bgives food to the hungry. The LORD ^csets the prisoners free.</p> <p>Psa. 146:8 The LORD ^aopens <i>the eyes</i> of the blind; The LORD ^braises up those who are bowed down; The LORD ^cloves the righteous; ⁹ The LORD ^{1a}protects the ²strangers; He ^{3b}supports the fatherless and the widow,</p>	<p>Psa. 146:1 הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה נַפְשִׁי אֶת-יְהוָה : ² אֶת-הַלְלָהּ יְהוָה בְּתִנִּי אֲזַמְּרָה לְאֵלֵי בְּעוֹדִי : ³ אַל-תִּבְטְחוּ בְּבָדִיכִים בְּכֶן-אָדָם יִשְׁאֵן לוֹ תִשְׁעָה : ⁴ תִּצָּא רוּחוֹ יִשָּׁב לְאֲדָמָתוֹ בַּיּוֹם הַהוּא אֲבָדוֹ עֲשֵׂתִנְתִּיו : ⁵ אֲשֶׁר־יִשְׁאֵל יַעֲקֹב בְּעוֹרֹו שְׁבָרוֹ עַל-יְהוָה אֱלֹהָיו : ⁶ עֲשֵׂה אֲשֶׁמֹו וְאֲרִץ אֶת-הַיָּם וְאֶת-כָּל-אֲשֶׁר-בָּם הַשָּׁמַיִם וְאֶמֶת לְעוֹלָם : ⁷ עֲשֵׂה מִשְׁפָּט לְעֹשִׂיקִים נָתַן לֶחֶם לְרַעֲבִים יְהוָה מִתִּיר אֲסוּרִים : ⁸ יְהוָה אִפְקֹת עוֹרִים יְהוָה זָקַף כְּפוּפִים יְהוָה אָהַב צַדִּיקִים : ⁹ יְהוָה אֲשַׁמֵּר אֶת-גֵּרִים יָתוּם וְאֶלְמָנָה יַעֲזֹר וְרִדָּף רְשָׁעִים יַעֲנֹת : ¹⁰ יִמְלֹךְ יְהוָה אֲלֵעוֹלָם אֲלֵתִּיבֹד צִיּוֹן לְדָר וְדָר הַלְלוּ-יְהוָה :</p>

But He ⁴ thwarts ⁶ the way of the wicked.	
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References

Psalm 146:1

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 103:1

Psalm 146:2

^aPs 63:4

^bPs 104:33

Psalm 146:3

¹Lit *a son of a man*

^aPs 118:9

^bPs 118:8; Is 2:22

^cPs 60:11; 108:12

Psalm 146:4

¹Lit *his earth*

^aPs 104:29

^bEccl 12:7

^cPs 33:10; 1 Cor 2:6

Psalm 146:5

^aPs 144:15; Jer 17:7

^bPs 71:5

Psalm 146:6

¹Or *truth*

^aPs 115:15; Rev 14:7

^bActs 14:15

^cPs 117:2

Psalm 146:7

^aPs 103:6

^bPs 107:9; 145:15

^cPs 68:6; Is 61:1

Psalm 146:8

^aMatt 9:30; John 9:7

^bPs 145:14

^cPs 11:7

Psalm 146:9

¹Or *keeps*

²Or *sojourners*

³Or *relieves*

⁴Lit *makes crooked*

^aEx 22:21; Lev 19:34

^bDeut 10:18; Ps 68:5

^cPs 147:6

Psalm 146:10

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aEx 15:18; Ps 10:16

Targum

Psa. 146:1 Hallelujah! Praise the name of the LORD, O my soul. ² I will sing praise, O LORD, in my lifetime, I will make music to my God while I exist. ³ You shall not place your trust in rulers, in a son of man who has no redemption. ⁴ His spirit will go away, he will return to his dust; on that day his plans perish. ⁵ Happy is he whose help is the God of Jacob, whose hope is in the LORD his God. ⁶ Who made heaven and earth, the sea and all that is in them, who keeps truth forever. ⁷ Who brings judgment for the oppressed, who gives food to the hungry; the LORD, who sets the prisoners free. ⁸ The LORD gives sight to foreigners, who are likened to the blind; the LORD lifts up those who are bowed down, the LORD loves the righteous. ⁹ The LORD protects the proselyte; he will support the widow and orphan, but will confound the way of the wicked. ¹⁰ The LORD will reign forever; your God, O Zion, for all generations. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This is a Psalm of hope and encouragement for the oppressed Jews in Exile in Babylon. The torture of being in Exile was a concern. The author wants to help the people to continue to praise the LORD even in Exile.

Notes on this Psalm

The Psalmist notes that there are people who place their ultimate trust in men and women. One's ultimate trust should be in the LORD. It is fine to trust people, but the ultimate trust should only be in the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

